

Views on Educational Philosophy of Mahatma Gandhi

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Introduction

Gandhiji, The great thinker and educational reformer regarded education as a potent force for social development and social reconstruction. According to Mahatma Gandhi, education is an activity which is necessary not only for social progress but also for moral, political and economic development. According to Gandhiji true education is “an all-round drawing out of the best in children and men-body, mind and spirit”.

We are in 21st century which is commonly known as “the century of development”. Gandhian principles of value system are something that blend the entire India at one point of time. It initiated a revolution, that took the whole of nation in its stamp and lasted till we were able to get independence. “This value system gave the nation the principle of truth, non-violence, Satyagraha which result in peoples”. We are still alarm by the uniqueness of Gandhiji’s principled approach. He endorsed simple living and high thinking while practicing.

At present economic and moral economic and moral right as well as value going down and lighting and exploiting. In the course of development, we have to think of this solution problems and try to find out the solution best suited to our needs. The best suited solution for the problem of contemporary world is to follow Gandhi Principal. It is Gandhi's philosophy can save us from predicament. Mahatma Gandhi Wanted to create a new society based on truth, non-violence, justice, equality and universal brotherhood. His Belief in universal compulsory education, with its emphasis on mother tongue is a philosophy which may be interrupted as pragmatic in approach.

Gandhian Philosophy:

Mahatma Gandhi is not nearly a political philosopher; it is a message and philosophy of life. His mission was to reconstruct India from below upwards a decentralized socio-political and economic order with India's myriad village as its base. He was very much concerned with the nature and poor deprived

and the downtrodden and has integer to alter the evil, social, economics system of people. Gandhi is universally known as the known as the most renowned also the kamala truth kamala nonviolence, tolerance, freedom and piece he was a leader of his people.

Education System

Education system proposed by Gandhi called as “basic education”. He mainly aims at the education in mother tongue and should be make children skilled and independent. More than ever before Gandhiji’s teachings are valid today, when people are trying to find solutions to the rampant greed, widespread, violence and run away consumptive style of Living. Education through medium of the strength tongue break of accordance which should exist by mother tongue. Foreign languages made the kids crammers and imitator, unfit for original work and thought Gandhi said “literacy in itself no education”. I would prefer the child education by it a handicraft. It perpetuates in radical restricting of sociology of school knowledge.in India “literacy of the lower caste” such as spinning, weaving leather work, book binding etc. would be central. Gandhi's education system has got them. It aims development of personality. Gandhi the truth development of head and soul necessary for satisfactory education. The wanted to construct self-reliant communities is ideal citizen all industries self-respecting and reliance communities, which is ideal citizens all industries and visual living in small committee stock Gandhiji said that the school must be an extension home must be a child gather at home and at school if the best result are to be obtained. Education through the medium of strength. We should exist of relationship are Enemies of the people their movies may be honest. To be a voluntary victim of the system education as the bay trial of our duty. Ham done by this alien type of education does not stop full stop it is so much further produced a Gulf between the educated classes and the message. Look on us as being apart from them of education Aim of education being an idealist and a realist advocated for ultimate and immediate aims of education. Self-realization Nezam and one with god is the ultimate aim of education. Great stress on religious education. in the immediate aim of education. Gandhiji included the utiliary m and harmonious development of personality. Fashion for completing living character building and training of good citizenship the chief ten of Gandhiji's Educational Philosophy maybe mention as:

- Free and compulsory primary education
- Education should be cracked concern
- Education should be unsuped and self sufficient
- Education should be given in mother tongue.

Concept of Basic Education

Basic education is the scheme of education Mahatma Gandhi. Construction of the existing system of education in India dash scheme of education is also known as Nainital game of education. Aur basically education is a philosophy of education by Mahatma Gandhi stone cultural social spiritual and economic need of the people of the country. Education for life and throughout life basic education is the fundamental education. fundamental to the whole scheme of education. Education was really the basic concept of education because

1. It attempts to provide the minimum of learning to be acquired by an average children.
2. It is directly linked with the basic Earth of human life.
3. It is mainly co related with the basic of the child.
4. It makes use of the native potentially of child.
5. It is closely related to the basic occupations of the community.

Philosophy behind the Gandhi's concept of education

Gandhi developed his scheme or planning of education in the light of his philosophy of life. His came of education is best on some fundamental ideas. these ideas are:

1. Ideal of classes' society.
2. Freedom and equality for all.
3. Dignity of labour.
4. Non wireless social order.
5. Development of sense of social responsibility.

Conclusion

The teaching of Mahatma Gandhi whole relevant even in today's Gandhi philosophy is not only simultaneously political moral and religious. it additional and modern simple and complex. Gandhi and philosophy of education is simultaneously traditional and modern. being rotate in Indian culture and heritage. the concept of Gandhian Educational Philosophy projected to the moral and ethical principles of our country. The multifaceted to nature of Gandhian throughout place his educational ideas head of its time. Gandhiji included all the needs of the present and coming social life in the process of his educational planning. due to all these matters Gandhian philosophy of education has its relevance in the present day social and National life.

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